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Data Management Report

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Abstract (for public dissemination only)	In this deliverable we provide an update on how the Data Management Plan (DMP) was implemented during the course of the mAKE project, the data handling during the project, and the data management after the official funding period.
Keywords	Data management, Open Science, RRI

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List of Abbreviations

AHIOSH	African Higher Institute of Open Science and Hardware
AI	artificial intelligence
DIH	Digital Innovation Hub
DI	digital innovation
DM	distributed manufacturing
DMP	Data Management Plan
DoA	Description of Action
ETL	extract, transform, load
EU	European Union
FAIR	findable, accessible, interoperable and reusable
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
GNU GPL	GNU General Public License
H2020	Horizon 2020 program of the European Union
IoP Alliance	Internet of Production Alliance
MiR	Maker-in-Residency
MOOC	massive open online course
NGO	non-governmental organisation
OCBM	Open Catalogue of Business Models
OKW	Open Know-Where

OSH	open source hardware
PU	public
RRI	Responsible Research and Innovation
SME	small and medium-sized enterprise
TVET	technical and vocational education and training
WP	work package

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Executive Summary

mAKE was an innovation action that aimed to promote cooperation and strategic partnerships between Digital Innovation Hubs (DIHs) in Africa and Europe. The DIHs in mAKE were makerspaces, which have been growing to become important actors in the local digital innovation ecosystems in both Europe and Africa. Makerspaces support digital, local manufacturing, and innovation in product design and development.

The mAKE project contributed to strengthening the EU-Africa innovation and start-up ecosystem by creating infrastructure for decentralised production and collaboration as well as shared policy frameworks and educational opportunities. The infrastructure allows for fast and efficient collaboration among the actors in the ecosystem in terms of knowledge-sharing, skills, use of machines and contracting processes in support of distributed manufacturing. The mAKE capacity-building activities equipped makerspaces and their attached local small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) and digital start-ups with the necessary skills to engage in hardware-based innovation and small-scale manufacturing. We offered learning resources, targeted trainings, and incubation, mentoring and matching activities for makers and makerspaces in Africa and Europe.

During the duration of the mAKE project, all work packages were managing data, guided by the Data Management Plan (DMP, D8.2) as well as the Project Handbook (D8.1). Personal data was primarily collected during events (for registration purposes) and when setting up interviews, and this data was then either deleted or anonymised. Non-personal data, such as the geographical location of machines and tools, was made publicly available online in compliance with the principles of open and public sharing of data.

As stated in the Grant Agreement, mAKE was part of the Open Research Data Pilot of the EU, and has thus been committed to providing access not only to project results and processes, but also to data collected during those processes, such as the open dataset for the project's map of machinery (Deliverable D4.3).

1. Introduction

This is the final report on data management in the mAKE project.

Two main documents served as guiding references for data management:

The Project Handbook (Deliverable D8.1) describes the internal procedures of the mAKE consortium in terms of management structures, communication and collaboration, as well as quality control measures. It also defines the ways in which the partners are dealing with Responsible Research and Innovation (RRI), especially considering ethical issues related to collection, analysis and storage of personal data. It also specifies the project's open source and open access strategy.

The Data Management Plan (DMP, Deliverable D8.2) describes the data management life cycle for the data to be collected, processed and/or generated by the mAKE project, following the Guidelines on FAIR Data Management in Horizon 2020 as provided by the European Commission. As part of making research data findable, accessible, interoperable and reusable (FAIR), the mAKE DMP includes information on:

- the handling of original data during and after the end of the project
- what data will be collected, processed and/or generated
- which methodology and standards will be applied
- whether data will be shared/made open access
- how data will be curated and preserved (including after the end of the project)

In addition, data management was performed in accordance with the confidential ethics deliverables D9.1 and D9.2.

In this report we give an overview of how the data was managed during the course of the mAKE project. We give a complete overview of all the data handled across the work packages and how the data will be handled after the end of the project.

The document is structured as follows:

- mAKE open resources: an overview of all mAKE open resources developed in the course of the project, including mAKE open data
- Future of mAKE data: plans for how the open data will be shared and made accessible beyond the lifetime of the project
- Conclusions: final conclusions on the process of data management, including issues encountered, lessons learnt
- Annex: detailed overview of data handled during mAKE arranged according to work packages

2. mAkE Open Resources

The mAkE consortium members have been committed to openness and sharing of resources throughout the project. Thus, all mAkE deliverables have been classified as public (PU) with respect to their dissemination level from the onset in the Description of Action (DoA). PU requires complete public access and thus, all deliverables have been made available on the project website and in the open repository Zenodo¹, as well as via OpenAIRE² and the EU Open Research Repository³.

More specifically the links to mAkE resources and data within these repositories are:

- Zenodo: <https://zenodo.org/communities/make/records>
- OpenAIRE: https://explore.openaire.eu/search/project?projectId=corda_h2020::e7577dc4e66a12ca2ec489c6e6cf679d
- EU Open Research Repository: <https://ec.europa.eu/info/funding-tenders/opportunities/portal/screen/opportunities/projects-details/31045243/101016858/H2020>

2.1 Open Data

As indicated in the Data Management Plan (D8.2) access to the collected data will be open and free while adhering to privacy and personal data protection. The following datasets have been created in mAkE and have been made publicly accessible:

Open Global Makerspaces dataset

These files contain data for makerspaces that are included in the map of makerspaces generated by the Internet of Production Alliance:

<https://explore.openaire.eu/search/dataset?pid=10.5281%2Fzenodo.8383704>

doi: [10.5281/zenodo.8383704](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8383704), [10.5281/zenodo.8383705](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8383705)

Makerspace Machines and Tools dataset

This dataset contains open data on the machines and tools available at the makerspaces listed in Open Global Makerspaces dataset:

<https://explore.openaire.eu/search/dataset?pid=10.5281%2Fzenodo.8383728>

¹ <https://zenodo.org/>

² <https://explore.openaire.eu/>

³ <https://research-and-innovation.ec.europa.eu>

doi: [10.5281/zenodo.8383728](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8383728), [10.5281/zenodo.8383729](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8383729)

- A Git repository containing Jupyter notebooks for the collection and analysis of data on makerspaces and machinery:
https://github.com/iop-alliance/okw_data_management/tree/main/notebooks/data_collectors
- A data completion script using natural language processing was executed. The detailed data analysis can be found in this notebook:
https://github.com/iop-alliance/data_reports/blob/main/notebooks/machines_in_fablab_world_tags.ipynb
- Machines catalogue repository, based on Open Know-Where (OKW) standard:
https://github.com/iop-alliance/okw_machines_catalog
- Database specification repository:
https://github.com/iop-alliance/okw_data_management/blob/main/docs/okw_v1_schema_specification.md
- Map of Machinery project documentation:
https://github.com/iop-alliance/okw_map_site/tree/web_page_site
- A comprehensive list of all data outputs for the Map of Machinery via OKW:
<https://map.internetofproduction.org/data/>
- Map of Machinery usage analytics:
<https://map.internetofproduction.org/analytics/>

2.2 Open Knowledge

Next to the open data, mAKE created an important set of resources for reuse that are available across different platforms, communities and networks. Here, we would like to highlight how mAKE results have already started to be shared in global maker communities as resources of open knowledge.

IoP Alliance community forum: <https://community.internetofproduction.org>

Business Models & Contracting channel in IoP Alliance community forum:
<https://community.internetofproduction.org/c/initiatives-channel/bmc/11>

mAKE Open Catalogue of Business Models (OCBM):
<https://localeconomies.org/manufacturingbusinessmodel-category/makerspaces/>

Roles in Distributed Manufacturing article by mAKE's Anna Sera Lowe:
<https://medium.com/internetofproduction/roles-in-distributed-manufacturing-2818381b49c7>

People and Skills channel in IoP Alliance community forum
<https://community.internetofproduction.org/c/initiatives-channel/people-skills/17>

Open Know-Where category in channel in IoP Alliance community forum:

<https://community.internetofproduction.org/c/okw/13>

mAKE community in IoP Alliance community forum:

<https://community.internetofproduction.org/c/communities/make-community/23>

2.3 Open Standards

The work in the mAKE project, and more specifically the work in work package 4, has contributed to the following open standards:

Mutual Recognition Standard for skills

doi: [10.5281/zenodo.8370683](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8370683) – File containing D4.1: Skills – Mutual Recognition Standard

PubPub: <https://standards.internetofproduction.org/pub/r7gOn9fo/release/4> –file, on PubPub open platform, containing the People and Skills specification

Open Know-Where (OKW) standard

<https://iopa.pubpub.org/pub/okw/release/1> – File containing OKW specification published on PubPub open platform: (www.pubpub.org)

2.4 Open Software

Map of Machinery

ETL (extract, transform, load) data aggregation system implementation:

https://github.com/iop-alliance/okw_data_management/tree/main/pipelines/metaflow

- Source pipelines are Python scripts for the downloading and processing of data for makerspaces and similar spaces and organisations.
- `__functions__` is a library for the processing of data points, using machine learning, for the clustering based on language processing and locations (latitude, longitude). Its purpose is to identify the same location reference in multiple data sources. It uses the open source Metaflow library under Apache 2.0.
- `__visualisations__` is a library for the rendering of data points into a Mercator projection map using the Folium library open-sourced under GNU GPL.

Visual design code repositories (code available in different programming languages):

- Python: https://github.com/iop-alliance/okw_data_management/blob/main/pipelines/metaflow/visualisations_.py

- JavaScript:
https://github.com/iop-alliance/okw_data_management/blob/main/pipelines/metaflow/assets/cluster_icon.js
- Code for the data validation function:
https://github.com/iop-alliance/okw_data_management/blob/main/pipelines/metaflow/__functions__.py

Contracts – Model and Prototype

The platform: <https://distributed-orders.fly.dev>

The source code for the front end of the order management system is openly licensed (MIT license) and available at this repository:

<https://github.com/iop-alliance/distributed-contracts-trials>

Many parts of the workflow automation were implemented using the open-source Active Pieces (www.activepieces.com) platform. The workflow used in the virtual trials are available at this repository for others to utilise: <https://github.com/iop-alliance/activepieces-flows>

2.5 Open Learning Resources

Next to the open knowledge resources, mAKE has developed two main open learning resources in work package 3, namely the Open Makerspace Tool and the mAKE MOOC.

- Open Makerspace Toolkit in OpenAIRE
doi: [10.5281/zenodo.10974525](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10974525), [10.5281/zenodo.10974526](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10974526)
- mAKE MOOC: <https://makeafricaeu.moodlecloud.com/>

2.6 Deliverables

All deliverables and open data sets linked to deliverables have been published in Zenodo, where a specific mAKE community has been established:

<https://zenodo.org/communities/make>

In addition, the deliverables are available on the mAKE website, which will be maintained for a minimum of 5 years after project end:

<https://makeafricaeu.org/>

3. The future of mAKE resources and data

The open data, knowledge, standards, software and learning resources of the mAKE project will continue to be used, maintained, developed and extended for years to come. Core measures to assure the accessibility and availability are:

- Using open licensing for all the mAKE resources and data outlined above
- Offering our resources and data on widely used open repositories that are supported by the EC
- Commitment to host the website for a minimum of 5 years after project end

WP6 includes development of a plan for the sustainability of the mAKE project outputs, and that plan also informs the future of mAKE data. The consortium members of the mAKE project will continue to use and develop the mAKE data created during this project as part of their routine business practices and purposes. In addition, a mAKE project legacy group plans to continue helping others to use the data and to find new projects where the mAKE data can receive further investments. This will be outlined in more detail in the deliverable D6.4 Sustainability Report.

For example, via the mAKE MOOC platform new online courses and learning resources will be invited and added. The platform will be supported by the African Higher Institute of Open Science and Hardware (AHIOSH)⁴, who will maintain and ensure the sustainability of the MOOC platform. In addition, the mAKE project legacy group will ensure that the MOOC will be made available to other projects for new content, such as learning on marketing and fundraising from the Innovative Manufacturing in Africa project—an IOP Alliance project linked to WP4—or content on innovation management from the AfriLabs community.

A more detailed outlook into the future of the project's additional knowledge products – such as the Venture Building Handbook and the Common Policy Agenda – will be addressed in other deliverables (including in the WP6 sustainability plan (D6.4: Sustainability Report)). Much of the data under management relates to the innovations developed under WP4. The planned future of these data products is outlined below.

The immediate commitment is that the consortium member IoP Alliance, which has led WP4, will continue to host, maintain and develop the data on makerspaces and machines, and the related standards and software, as part of its routine work of enabling distributed manufacturing (DM). The IoP Alliance will continue to ensure compliance with open publishing and data protection regulations in different jurisdictions. The data systems that support these innovations will be continuously updated, maintained and backed up.

The IoP Alliance also intends to build on the data with continuous updates and improvements, including through other funded projects in Africa, Europe and other regions

⁴ <https://www.ahiosh.org/>

of the world. For example, in its other work, the IoP Alliance supports “data awards” for people around the world to map machines, and is planning to establish a prototype “maker passport” platform on which makers can manage and update their skill profiles. The IoP Alliance is also exploring other innovative approaches to further development of the data generated by mAKE WP4, such as:

Makerspaces:

- Team up on projects with emerging makerspace associations in other parts of the world, such as in South Asia, the Philippines and the US.
- Team up with corporations that have private-sector makerspaces – such as big tech companies.
- Embed the open standards into makerspace management software products.
- Continue to present the innovations at makerspace conferences in the years to come.
- Diversify the community with outreach to other movements (e.g. Men’s Sheds).

Machines and Tools:

- Engage with manufacturers of digital fabrication machines to embed the open standards into the firmware of their machines – following the lead of the French 3D printer firm CosMYX.
- Engage with machine manufacturers to spread awareness of the innovations using their customer databases and mailing lists.
- Introduce new software tools that make it easier to add machines to the map of machinery, and to find machines nearby.
- Engage with other networks that have existing datasets that have not yet been engaged with, such as manufacturers associations, trade bodies and industry magazines.
- Explore the opportunities for data aggregation for the provision of artificial intelligence (AI) services where the data and standards could provide valuable services in data labelling that is essential to AI tools. This approach takes inspiration from the way that datasets and systems like *OpenStreetMap* provide data for the geographic mapping community. Indeed, AI tools for enabling DM could become a central part of the roadmap for these innovations.
- Extend efforts to make the mAKE project data more inclusive by finding ways to reach out to places that have been difficult to reach during the project, such as Somalia, South Sudan, or Burundi. This could be done by using the most common data services, and also through non-governmental organisation (NGO) partners that are active in those places. Essentially, it would mean placing these innovations in the impact chains of other projects and organisations so that they add value to their work. An example might be a technical and vocational education and training (TVET)

programme in Somalia where an NGO is supporting technical colleges to train young people in tailoring or vehicle maintenance.

- Explore more scenarios for the use of the map of machinery.

People and Skills:

- Deliverable D4.2 (Skills – Maker Passports & Prototype) describes next steps, including the development of mutual recognition systems and standards between makerspaces.
- Team up with networks of makerspaces to test maker passport badging systems based on pre-existing systems for issuance of credentials, as detailed in the D4.2. This would help increase understanding of user behaviours and how the maker passport is used in various regions.
- An immediate next step will be the launch of a prototype maker passport platform where makers can create profiles showcasing their certifications, trainings, skills and achievements (portfolios, testimonials). Via this platform, makers would find potential collaborators, mentors, clients, or projects to join.
- Continue the development of community-based authentication, and the development of a community-centered authentication platform (using Kee).

Contracting for Distributed Manufacturing:

- Continue the research and testing, in various regions, of the contracting prototype system developed.
- Extend the trials to include larger organisations, SMEs, entrepreneurs, NGOs and public sector institutions to identify different DM scenarios and the contracting relationships. Invest in extending the research for more learnings and use cases.
- Develop a DM catalogue.
- Develop a catalogue of DM contracting models.
- Expand the mAKE OCBM to include additional areas related to makerspaces, such as business models for open hardware manufacturing, so as to ensure that the catalogue continues to evolve and grow as new content is researched and developed.

In the long term, individuals will have the ability to manage and update their data on a maker passport platform, utilising the developed tools to connect with other skilled makers for collaboration, project replication, or direct order fulfillment. With open access to all data, transparency and traceability will be central to DM via local production, driving greater adoption of this model.

To further promote DM success, collecting and showcasing success stories will be crucial. By documenting real-world examples of how people are effectively using the tools, these stories can be shared in papers, books, and case studies. This will inspire others to engage with the model, highlighting the tangible benefits and creative possibilities. Sharing these narratives will also serve as a feedback loop, helping refine the tools and approaches based on user experiences, ultimately fostering a more collaborative and innovative ecosystem.

4. Conclusions

This document has presented the details of how the project managed the data across all workpackages and practiced openness. While mAKE is fully committed to open science and openness as defaults, the privacy and security of personal data coming from our research participants has been of the highest priority. Informed consent procedures were applied.

Section 4 above outlines the future of the mAKE open resources, and we are confident that the commitment to openness will be beneficial and create a positive long-term impact across the African, European, and global communities of makers and makerspaces.

5. References

Kieslinger, B., & Schuch, K. (2022). Data Management Plan. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7628424>

Kieslinger, B., Schaefer, T., & Fabian, C. M. (2023). mAKE Project Handbook. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7635757>

6. Annex 1: Data Overview

The following table provides an overview of all the data handled in the mAKE project.

Work package & data collection activity	Short description of data & aim of the data	Type of data (observational, experimental,, ...) ⁵	Type of files / data format (DOCX, ODF, ODT, PDF, CVS, JPEG, ...)	Reuse, if applicable, of existing data	Data management after project completion
WP1_D1.1 Database of Business Models	Documentation of business models (using Business Model Canvas framework). Was subject to “Informed Consent” procedure and the information was not shared in a way that it can be linked to a particular respondent. The data was used to build abstracted models that were shared.	Observational: Interview responses	XLS PDF Audio files [mp3 / mp4]	No reuse of pre-existing data. Use of data compiled by the project in WP2;	No personal data has been stored; The result of this activity is an Open Catalogue of Business Models, which is being offered on various platforms as an open learning resource (incl. the mAkE website, Zenodo)
WP1_T1.2 Venture Building and Business Development	Data was collected via Google Forms and via an online data room in GreenTech’s Sharepoint during the application process for the venture building activities and matchmaking purposes. The	Event-related; Derived or Compiled	DOC/DOCX/ODT XLS PDF	No reuse of pre-existing data. Use of data compiled by the project	Personal data has not been stored. The data room and especially pitch decks will be stored for the purposes of due diligence in case investors are showing interest in the companies even after the program. Data

⁵ A detailed description of the types of data is provided in the Data Management Plan (D8.2.).

	<p>applicants enter information themselves, such as:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Contact details - Collection of business related data - Collection of founder related data such as name, experience, expertise etc. - Collection of DIH related data 				room will only be shared if approved by the company.
<p>WP1_ T 1.3 Matchmaking: Hub-to-Hub, Founder-to-Founder & Business-to-Business</p>	<p>Data Collection of:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Data relating to DIHs offering Hub-to-Hub residency programs - Collection of data relating to African DIH looking for Hub-to-Hub makers-in-residency programmes - Data collection done through interviews and online research. <p>In the course of the Maker-in-Residency (MiR),</p>	Derived or compiled	DOC/DOCX/ODT XLS PDF	<p>No reuse of pre-existing data</p> <p>Use of data compiled by the project</p>	Data will be deleted at the end of the project.

	personal and project-related data had to be collected in order to select candidates together with the jury, to book flights, support with invitation letters for the Schengen Visa etc.				
WP2_Hub Ecosystem and Policy Frameworks WP2_ T2.1 Explore current approaches to multi-actor policy guidance	<p>-Collection of data from collective associations on how they began operations and the value they offer to their members.</p> <p>-Collection of data from makerspaces on their operations and their involvement with Collective Associations.</p> <p>-The aim of both is to understand current structures supporting makerspaces and come up with policy</p>	qualitative data; interview responses	DOC PDF Audio files	No reuse of pre-existing data Use of data compiled by the project	No personal data has been stored; The result of this activity is a series of case studies published in the deliverable D2.1 <i>Report on National and Regional Hub Association including 7 documented Case studies and comparative analysis</i> . It has been published in agreement with the involved individuals and is openly accessible via the mAKE website and Zenodo.

	<p>recommendations that will support makerspaces.</p> <p>informed consent procedures were followed</p>				
<p>WP2_ T2.3 Develop practice-based, common policy frameworks</p>	<p>Documentation of focus group discussions, one-to-one interviews and a community call to collect input for the policy framework (Deliverable D2.2_Common Policy Agenda and Recommendations for Policy Makers)</p>	<p>Observational, Qualitative</p>	<p>Consent forms, DOC</p> <p>Survey responses (XLS)</p> <p>Video</p> <p>Audio files (mp4)</p>	<p>Reuse of WP2_T2.1 data</p>	<p>No personal data involved.</p> <p>The result of this activity is the Common Policy Agenda including recommendations for policy makers, and strategies for engaging policy makers. It is accessible via mAkE website, and Zenodo.</p>
<p>WP2_ T2.4 Framework in practice and dissemination</p>	<p>Minister meets Makers dialogue events documentation</p>	<p>Observational, Qualitative</p>	<p>DOC</p> <p>Audio file (mp4)</p> <p>video</p>	<p>Reuse of data compiled in WP2.</p> <p>Use of data compiled by the project</p>	<p>No personal or sensitive data involved.</p> <p>The result of this activity involves series of workshops and events such as the Ghana Hubs Network Annual General Meeting, Ghana</p>

					Digital Innovation Week 2023, and 2024, Transformation Literacy Conference 2024, virtual, Wind Empowerment Conference in Greece, Vulca Coference in Germany, mAKE talk video, Afrilabs Impact presentation, Distributed Design Platform and mAKE collaborative policy workshop, AfricaOSH workshop A-MEG policy workshop. They are accessible on via mAKE website and social media, and youtube.
WP3: Open Education, Skill Development and Capacity Building WP3_T3.1 Develop an Open Makerspace Toolkit	Collection of existing content and learning materials, and content created for this project from consortium partners. -collection of relevant data (models, maps, case studies) from other WP's in order to enrich the toolkit.	Qualitative	DOC, PDF audio files, video files	re-use of existing contents and learning materials provided by consortium partners.	No sensitive data involved; the collected data is available as an online toolkit openly accessible via the mAKE website and Zenodo

WP3_T3.2_Host Training of Trainers	Feedback was collected from trainers and trainees attending the events	Event-related; Questionnaire, qualitative feedback	DOC; PDF; Videos	No re-use of pre-existing data	Personal data will not be stored; the feedback was taken up to improve the training sessions and feed into WP7.
WP3_T3.3_ Develop and implement the mAKE MOOC, a shared online platform	Collection of recorded videos of practical training, practical skills, existing and newly created open source training, open education resources and courses. The aim is to make them available online so that innovators, makers, promoters and the interested public can receive life long education	Qualitative	Video formats	Use of T3.2 data	No personal data; the data is compiled and available as an open learning course for the next 5 years (min).
WP4 D4.1 Skills – Mutual Recognition Standard	Contact details and interview notes for scoping exercise research to inform the development of the skills standard; contact details of voluntary community of interested parties which acts as	Qualitative, and experimental	XLSX/spreadsheets DOC, PDF, audio files	No re-use of pre-existing data	To be maintained on PubPub online platform; email lists and membership lists hosted by Internet of Production (IOP)

	<p>the reference group for the skills standard.</p> <p>Name, contact and affiliation data; written notes; aggregated and interpreted written findings.</p>				
<p>WP4 D4.2 Skills – Maker Passports & Prototype</p>	<p>Unique identifier as assigned, name, address/location, contact details, skills, third-party verifications / recommendations, profile picture/ personal avatar</p>	<p>Qualitative, and experimental</p>	<p>XLSX/spreadsheet; HTML (potentially online profiles supported by secured databases) image (JPEG)</p>	<p>No re-use of pre-existing data</p>	<p>In the future this will be offered as a tool where individuals are offered to share their skills and any personal information according to Open Know How standard. This will be managed by IOP.</p>
<p>WP4 D4.3 Machinery - Map</p>	<p>Detailed data on machines/tools as defined by Open Know-Where standard; contact details of machine/tool owner; address/location data; machines/tools</p> <p>Primarily focus on data collection to form and enhance digital manufacturing related</p>	<p>Quantitative, experimental</p>	<p>Database supporting an online map tool; images. CSV, JSON, GEOJS, KML.</p>	<p>The data system collects data from multiple open, public published sources, and in compliance with GDPR and other data privacy regulations. It also provides forms for new data entries.</p>	<p>Data expiration: Data would be re-validated or discarded after 36 months from the initial date of data publishing. More details are described under our data privacy policy. [https://map.internetofproduction.org/data-privacy-policy/index.html] The Internet of Production Alliance holds an enhanced</p>

	data, such as machinery technical specifications, and locations with their manufacturing capabilities.				version of published data and redistributes data depending on the data source's licensing. All data selected and analyzed compliance with open and public sharing scientific and creative data licensing.
WP4 D4.4 Contracts – Model & Prototype	<p>For the model contract: To inform the design of the model contract, contact details and interview notes for scoping exercise research.</p> <p>For the prototype: Data on location of machines/tools and maker passport profiles enables users to determine who can make what product where, and then issue a model contract to them for production to begin.</p> <p>For the pilot trial: Name, contact details, address/location, machine ownership/access, maker passport profile, contract</p>	Experimental	Database supporting software for automated contracting system prototype	No re-use of pre-existing data	No personal data will be stored after the virtual pilot in WP4.

	terms data (such as design, quantity, price, terms etc) and payment data (such as bank details, KYC data).				
WP5_KPIs Communication & Dissemination Outreach	Collection of statistic data: Social media statistics Google analytics for the website	Event-related, Derived or Compiled	XLSX/spreadsheets , DOC/DOCX/ODT, PDF, JPEG, Audio and Video files [mp3 / mp4]	No reuse of pre-existing data Use of data compiled by the project	No personal data; Data was used for reporting purposes; will be stored for project documentation purposes;
WP5_Communication, Dissemination and Outreach	Newsletter; self-subscribed mailing list: Name and contact details of subscribers	Event-related	Collected in Mailchimp	No reuse of pre-existing data Use of data compiled by the project	The self-subscribed e-mail addresses are stored by Mailchimp and GDPR compliant; the new secretariat, which will be set up as part of the sustainability plan of mAKE is planning to keep the mailing list and maintain it
WP5_T5.4 Define and develop guidelines for	A collection of materials, formats, values, guidelines on how-to for webinars, filming,	Observational Derived - Compiled	XLSX/spreadsheets , DOC/DOCX/ODT, PDF, JPEG, Audio	No reuse of pre-existing data Use of data compiled by the project	No personal data collected;

capacity building tools	write blog posts, post and make citations.		and Video files [mp3 / mp4]		The results are available as open data on the mAKE website and Zenodo
WP5_KPIs - Communication & Dissemination Outreach	For the tracking of the project KPIs data was collected regarding mAKE public events via an internal event tracker filled by consortium partners Interviews with consortium partners: Name and contact details of consortium partners	Event-related	XLSX/spreadsheets DOC/DOCX/ODT PDF JPEG Audio and Video files [mp3 / mp4] videos	No reuse of pre-existing data Use of data compiled by the project	No personal data; Data was used for reporting purposes; will be stored for project documentation purposes;
WP6_D6.1 Community Activation & Engagement Strategy	For the management of the community and the engagement strategy contact details were collected from the consortium members and their communities	Observational, Event-related, Derived or Compiled	XLSX/spreadsheet, DOC/DOCX/ODT, PDF, JPEG, Audio and Video files [mp3 / mp4]	Member lists of consortium partner communities	The results are available as open data on the mAKE website and Zenodo

<p>WP6_D6.2 Co-Creation Report</p>	<p>Documentation of experiences made by the consortium partners during the co-creation activities</p>	<p>Observational, Event-related, Derived or Compiled</p>	<p>DOC/DOCX/ODT, PDF, JPEG, Audio and Video files [mp3 / mp4]</p>	<p>No reuse of pre-existing data</p>	<p>Partner internal data only; will not be shared publicly; only in an aggregated version; Aggregated version available after project end on mAKE project website and Zenodo.</p>
<p>WP6_Task_6.3 Sharing & Embedding Strategy</p>	<p>Develop a sharing and embedding strategy (in collaboration with WP5) Ensure community engagement in the development of capacity building materials, trainings and other open educational resources (resources developed in WP1, WP2, WP3, WP4) Offer webinars, offline meetups, and peer to peer learning sessions Facilitate knowledge transfer on licensing and open repositories.</p>	<p>Observational, Event-related, Derived or Compiled</p>	<p>XLSX/spreadsheets , DOC/DOCX/ODT, PDF, JPEG, Audio and Video files [mp3 / mp4]</p>	<p>Member contacts, website contacts, newsletter contacts</p>	<p>No personal data collected; Available as a deliverable on mAKE project website and Zenodo</p>

D8.4 Data Management Report

WP6: D6.4 Sustainability Report	The legacy of the mAKE project with a plan of action as part of an overall strategy and report.	Observational, Event-related, Derived or Compiled	DOC/DOCX/ODT, PDF, JPEG	No reuse of pre-existing data	No personal data collected; Available as a deliverable on mAKE project website and Zenodo
WP7_Interviews with participants of the MiR programme	Collection of statements from participants of the MiR programme; the data are subject to the informed consent procedure described in D8.1 “Project Handbook”.)	Qualitative and quantitative data	DOC/DOCX/ODT, Audio files [mp3 / mp4]	No reuse of pre-existing data Use of data compiled by the project	On ZSI servers for project documentation purpose for the duration of 5 years; In an compiled version as part of the deliverables of WP7 available on the mAKE website and Zenodo. Summaries of interviews together with selected individual statements published as impact stories on the mAKE website after approval of interview partners
WP7_Interviews with makerspace managers, start-ups and small business	Collection of statements from makerspace managers, start-up representatives and small businesses and entrepreneurs about mAKE products, such as	Observational, qualitative data recorded and transcribed	DOC/DOCX/ODT, Audio files [mp3 / mp4]	No reuse of pre-existing data Use of data compiled by the project	On ZSI servers for project documentation purpose for the duration of 5 years;

and entrepreneurs in maker spaces	the company builder programmes, the open catalogue of business models, maker passport, ToTs on the makerspace toolkit etc; the data are subject to the informed consent procedure described in D8.1 “Project Handbook”.)				<p>In an compiled version as part of the deliverables of WP7 available on the mAKE website and Zenodo,</p> <p>Summaries of interviews together with selected individual statements published as impact stories on the mAKE website after approval of interview partners</p>
WP7_survey data	Collection of online surveys regarding mAKE products, such as venture building ToTs, policy recommendations, ToTs on the makerspace toolkit.	Qualitative and quantitative data	XLS/ HTML, or other Web coding language	The data will be used internally for the project evaluation	<p>No personal data stored after the project: Only available in compiled and anonymized version</p> <p>Available as part of WP7 deliverables on mAKE project website and Zenodo.</p>
WP7_Evaluation workshop data	Project team and selected case participants are invited to give their feedback on mAKE products and services in collaborative evaluation	Event-related, observational	extracts from Miro Board and other collaboration tools (PDF, JPEG), audio recordings,	The data will be used internally for the project evaluation and to elaborate the final mAKE products and services	<p>No personal data collected;</p> <p>Available as part of WP7 deliverables on mAKE project website and Zenodo</p>

	workshops (e.g. on the distributed contracting system)		protocols as DOC/DOCX/ODT		
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Table 01: mAKE data overview

